

Benchmark list

1. Asche, F., Guttormsen, A.G. and Tveterås, R., 1999. Environmental problems, productivity and innovations in Norwegian salmon aquaculture. *Aquaculture Economics & Management*, 3(1), pp.19-29.
2. Boissy, J., Aubin, J., Drissi, A., van der Werf, H.M., Bell, G.J. and Kaushik, S.J., 2011. Environmental impacts of plant-based salmonid diets at feed and farm scales. *Aquaculture*, 321(1-2), pp.61-70.
3. Folke, C., Kautsky, N. and Troell, M., 1994. The costs of eutrophication from salmon farming: implications for policy. *Journal of environmental management*, 40(2), pp.173-182.
4. Ford, J.S., Pelletier, N.L., Ziegler, F., Scholz, A.J., Tyedmers, P.H., Sonesson, U., Kruse, S.A. and Silverman, H., 2012. Proposed local ecological impact categories and indicators for life cycle assessment of aquaculture: a salmon aquaculture case study. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 16(2), pp.254-265.
5. Ford, J.S. and Myers, R.A., 2008. A global assessment of salmon aquaculture impacts on wild salmonids. *PLoS biology*, 6(2), p.e33.
6. Naylor, R.L., Goldberg, R.J., Mooney, H., Beveridge, M., Clay, J., Folke, C., Kautsky, N., Lubchenco, J., Primavera, J. and Williams, M., 1998. Nature's subsidies to shrimp and salmon farming. *Science*, 282(5390), pp.883-884.
7. Newton, R.W. and Little, D.C., 2018. Mapping the impacts of farmed Scottish salmon from a life cycle perspective. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 23, pp.1018-1029.
8. Philis, G., Ziegler, F., Jansen, M.D., Gansel, L.C., Hornborg, S., Aas, G.H. and Stene, A., 2022. Quantifying environmental impacts of cleaner fish used as sea lice treatments in salmon aquaculture with life cycle assessment. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 26(6), pp.1992-2005.
9. Phillips, M.J., Beveridge, M.C.M. and Ross, L.G., 1985. The environmental impact of salmonid cage culture on inland fisheries: present status and future trends. *Journal of fish Biology*, 27, pp.123-137.
10. Whitmarsh, D. and Wattage, P., 2006. Public attitudes towards the environmental impact of salmon aquaculture in Scotland. *European Environment*, 16(2), pp.108-121.
11. Arechavala-Lopez, P., Toledo-Guedes, K., Izquierdo-Gomez, D., Šegvić-Bubić, T. and Sanchez-Jerez, P., 2018. Implications of sea bream and sea bass escapes for sustainable aquaculture management: a review of interactions, risks and consequences. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, 26(2), pp.214-234.
12. Sánchez, J.L.F., Le Breton, A., Brun, E., Vendramin, N., Spiliopoulos, G., Furones, D. and Basurco, B., 2022. Assessing the economic impact of diseases in Mediterranean grow-out farms culturing European sea bass. *Aquaculture*, 547, p.737530.